

ISSN : 2746-8402

Indexed by:

ROAD

zenodo

INTERNATIONAL VIRTUAL CONFERENCE ON

LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE PROCEEDING

Publisher: Malang, Politeknik Negeri Malang
Medium: Online
Country: Indonesia

Editorial Team

Dr. Oro Cabanas

Available at <http://ivicollpolinema.com/index.php/ll>

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International Virtual Conference on Language and Literature Proceeding.

Conference form: correspondence Internet conference.

Working languages: Indonesian, Russian, Uzbek, and English.

Indexed Google scholar, Zenodo

Part 2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5979515>

Indonesia 2022

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LITERATURE

**ELIJAH BALEY AS THE PREVAILING CHARACTER IN ISAAC
ASIMOV'S DETECTIVE SCIENCE FICTION**

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Annotation:

The article reveals the role of Elijah Baley as the protagonist of several science fiction detective novels by the American writer Isaac Asimov, including “The Caves of Steel”, “The Naked Sun”, and “The Robots of Dawn”. Baley is also mentioned in “Robots and Empire”, “Prelude to Foundation” and “Foundation and Earth”. Being prevailing personage Baley unites these novels into the series. Baley is given the role of the savior of mankind from degradation and death in the “the caves of steel”.

Keywords: Asimov, science fiction, detective, Elijah Baley, “The Caves of Steel”, “The Naked Sun”, “The Robots of Dawn”, robot, spacer.

Introduction. Elijah Baley is a policeman of the huge City of the future. Such Cities are called “the caves of steel” by I. Asimov. Baley investigates several crimes on Earth, Aurora and Solaria and becomes a partner and friend of the humanoid robot R. Daneel Olivaw and pushes him to formulate the Zeroth Law of Robotics about the primacy of the interests of mankind over the interests of individuals, and also helps him to become more “humane” [1, p. 54]. After communicating with the Spacers, inhabitants of the Outer Worlds, Baley turns into one of the main propagandists for the resettlement of earthlings to other planets. Elijah has not very high career growth abilities. His appearance is also not at all heroic. But Baley is able to think outside the box, has a developed sense of duty, is not devoid of common sense, endowed with a strong will and a complex tough character. Like Sherlock Holmes, he is a pipe-smoker, a habit he fights against in “The Robots of Dawn”. He is incapable of conformism, which prevented him from making a career. He believes that restoring

justice is more important than following the letter of the law. He can feel empathy for the criminal if he does not see malicious intent in his actions and believes that he does not pose a danger to society (for example, Julius Enderby and Gladia Delmarre). Like all earthlings of his era, Baley suffers from agoraphobia. He is ready to sacrifice personal interests for the deal. He is inclined to believe relatives and friends (for example, he did not suspect medievalists in his wife Jessie and his friend Julius). He is fond of history, especially the study of the customs of people in different eras. His worldview is a skeptic, but not without faith in high ideals.

“The Caves of Steel”. Elijah's life changes after his boss, Julius Enderby, sends him to investigate the murder of spacer Roj Nemennuh Sarton in Spacetown. The crime is very serious and capable of causing an interplanetary scandal, so Baley is promised a promotion to C7-class for solving it. Enderby, who was himself an unwitting criminal (he wanted to kill not a man, but a robot) hopes that Baley will not cope with the task. The Spacers approved Baley's candidacy for the role of detective, but had their own secret goal. The spacer Han Fastolfe, the leader of a party that advocates cooperation between the Earth and the Outer Worlds in further space exploration, hopes to solve the problem with the help of Baley: how to get earthlings to start colonizing planets that have not yet been explored and create a culture in which robots would play a significant role (“culture of Ce/Fe”). Baley finds the real killer and, in addition, comes to the conclusion that it is the medievalists who, according to their psychotype, are suitable for colonizing other planets. He forces Julius Enderby to help him organize the colonization. Moreover, during the investigation, Baley becomes a kind of friend with the robot Daneel Olivaw – his partner, whom the spacers imposed on him. Baley sees in Daneel Olivaw not just a machine but a sentient being close to a human being. Daneel also learns a lot from Baley.

“The Naked Sun”. In “The Naked Sun”, the story takes place a few years after the events of “The Caves of Steel”. Bailey, a C7-class detective, is assigned to investigate a murder on one of the Spacer's planets – Solaria. Baley was chosen by the Spacers (thanks to the assistance of Han Fastolfe), but the authorities of the Earth

give Baley an additional task – to study the life of one of the Outer Worlds and identify the weak points of the Spacers (since Baley is the first Earthman allowed to visit the Spacers’ planet). The Spacers assign R. Daneel Olivaw to Baley to help the detective. Solaria is an extremely robotic planet, people live in their estates full of robots and have completely switched to video communication, except when physical contact is necessary. On Solaria, personal contact is considered shameful, and children are selected and raised by robots and fetologists (specialists in selection and education of children) on special farms. Due to the lack of personal contacts, there are no murders on the planet, and when one happened, the intervention of an earthly policeman was required. The fetologist Rikaine Delmarre, best example of Solarian, a cold and insensitive individualist, was killed. Being accused of murder, his wife Gladia was an abstract artist, an emotional and vulnerable woman who had an abnormal for Solarians increased propensity for personal contacts. Baley finds out that, indeed, Gladia became an unwitting killer, but the murder was organized by the crazy and brilliant roboticist Jothan Leebig, who designed robots that were devoid of the First Law of Robotics, that is, that could harm people. Having visited the Solaria, Baley got rid of agoraphobia and realized that the strength of the Spacers – large cities, long life, and robots – is their weakness at the same time. All this contributes to the fact that the Spacers are afraid to risk their lives and thus lose the ability to develop.

“The Robots of Dawn”. Elijah Baley’s adventures continue in “The Robots of Dawn”. Baley is assigned to go to Aurora to investigate the crime - the incapacitation of a robot named R. Jander Panell. The robot belonged to Gladia who moved to Aurora and whom she considered her husband. The robot was designed by Han Fastolfe and it was Fastolfe who was accused of damaging it. Fastolfe’s enemies – his daughter Vasilisa Aliena and the director of the Institute of Robotics Kelden Amadiro – dreamed of using humanoid robots to colonize the Galaxy by the forces of the Spacers themselves, without the help of earthlings, whom they considered representatives of an inferior race. They believed that the damage to the robot was beneficial to Fastolfe, as it helped him to destroy their plans. Baley managed to prove

that Fastolfe is innocent and that Fastolfe's enemies, Vasilisa and Amadiro, who secretly tested Jander and corrupted his brain, are indirectly responsible for damaging the robot. Baley also guessed that the true organizer and performer of the crime was the telepathic robot R. Giskard Reventlov, who thus kept the secret of the technology for creating humanoid robots. In addition, Giskard used his abilities to lure Baley to Aurora and inspire Han Fastolfe that it is possible to describe the behavior of people and human groups with the help of mathematics (allusion to "psychohistory" created by Harry Seldon in the series of Asimov's novels "Foundation").

Conclusion. In the era of the Galactic Empire of "The Foundation" series, Baley turns into a folklore character. In "Prelude to Foundation", a storyteller mentions mother Rita, who tells several legends about Baley and Daneel. In "Foundation and Earth", the historian Janov Pelorat also mentions legends about Bailey and expresses the belief that this is a collective image. But 20000-year-old robot Daniel Olivaw states that Baley is not a fictional or imaginary character, that without him, the Earth would not have begun the colonization of the Outer Worlds (and neither the Galactic Empire nor the Foundation would have arisen), and that in memory of Baley, he helped the remnants of earthling's fight radiation on their planet and then relocated them to another planet. To conclude, the character of Elijah Baley is a key personage that unites the series of novels and stories written by Isaac Asimov. This prevailing character allowed the writer to harmonically unite the literary traditions of detective (crime) story and science fiction [2, p. 5] and create the amazing, mysterious and unique world.

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